

A review and generation of electricity from waste tyres by using pyrolysis technology

S. Priyadharsini¹, C. Kannan^{1,*}, S. Sivakumar¹ and T. S. Balajidamodhar²

¹ Arunai Engineering College, Tiruvannamalai – 606603, TamilNadu, India.

² Madanapalle Institute of Technology and Science, Madanapalle-517325, Andhra Pradesh, India.

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Abstract

This paper explores and debates the evolution process of pyrolysis of the waste tyre and the purpose of the subsequent products. The removal of used tyres from automotive vehicles becomes endless. Even though there are many procedures, there is a predicament to discard the unused tyres. Pyrolysis of a substance offers value-added products such as pyrolysis oil which is used for lubrication of high capacity furnace and power transformers. The existing method is pyro oil getting from waste tyres and excess uncondensed gas is wasted. In this paper, the discussions and applications of oil, charcoal, gas, and steel wires were elaborated.

Keywords: Waste Tyres; Pyrolysis; Pyro Oil; Uncondensed Gas; Electricity

1. Introduction

Globally, billions of waste unused tyres are available. It is impossible to burn or bury those tyres due to environmental pollutions. But, waste tyres cannot be reused in any way. A new product called pyro oil, char, and some other products can be extracted by pyrolysis. This process is not well established in India.

The procedure of pyrolysis maintains the temperature between 400 and 600°C in a nitrogen-purged stationary-bed batch reactor to pyrolyze the ragged scrap tyres. The condensers in series fascinate the oil and increase the gas production. The condensed oil with good fuel properties such as good calorific value, flash point, moisture content, fluorine, and chlorine contents were determined. The analysis of the concentration of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAH) and lighter aromatic hydrocarbons was executed in this process. The resultant tyre oil extracted has the property of a light petroleum fuel oil. The increase in pyrolysis temperature increases the perfume of the oil and results in a drop in aliphatic contents. Simultaneously, the PAH value was made to increase from 1.5 to 3.5 %. Methylfluorenes, tri- and tetra-methylphenanthrenes, and chrysene components were present in this concentration [1]. A detailed study was undergone to analyze the triangular procedure such as gathering the information by visiting the plants, by having personal and cellular communications, and by the literature surveys. The main merits and demerits of the pyrolysis process were elaborated in [2].

Product allocation depends upon the rate of cooling and temperature of the process. The slow pyrolysis process happens at low temperatures and can be utilized to maximize the solid char. A large amount of liquid products can be extracted by condensing the gas molecules by using rapid cooling. Nearly 80% of liquid can be extracted by adopting the proper pyrolysis process as in [3]. During the pyrolysis, the steam or hydrogen was tattered in the product distribution. Hydrogen plays a vital role in chemical reduction and maintaining the oxygen in the feedstock. At low temperature and high pressure, steam is used as the pyrolyzing medium. Water may be used as the pyrolyzing media by using the feedstock in the reactor and results in char with high surface and porous as in [4]. Pyrolysis is an endothermic

*Corresponding author: C Kannan

Arunai Engineering College, Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Tiruvannamalai, India.

progression that induces the thermal disintegration of feed materials without the addition of any hasty gases, such as air or oxygen. The thermal competence of this method is approximately 70%, and can augment to 90% with the exploit of pyrolysis harvest as fuel [5].

2. A view of Pyrolysis yield

2.1. Pyrolysis Gas

By increasing the pyrolysis temperature, the weight increases by 35%. The calorific value of the gas dissipated will be around 40MJ N/m³ and it is sufficient to supply the energy demand to small-scale industry. Hydrogen sulfide is a product of the vulcanized rubber and has low absorption [6].

2.2. Pyrolysis Oil

Alternative to fossil fuel is necessary to have green fuel to meet out the challenges such as environmental pollution, diminishing of fuel, and increase in the price of the fuel. Figure 1 elaborates the possible major range of utilizes and their production process. The unused waste pyrolytic liquid is an organic versatile in dark brown with a muscular choking odor. The pyrolytic oil should be utilized with high precautions due to its reactive properties such as creates rashes in the skin with the pungent smell for some days along with the yellowish-brown marks. his complexion is difficult to vanish even with the help of detergents. The composition of the tyre extracted oil contains naphthalene, phenanthrenes, alkylated benzenes, n- alkanes from C11 to C24, and alkenes from C8 to C15, with small quantities of nitrogen, sulphur, and oxygenated compound [7]. Industrial furnaces, power plants, and boilers use this oil as the liquid fuel and the has a quite low ash content and lingering carbon.

2.3. Activated Carbon

Water purification and air purification are possible by the activated carbon obtained from char from the tyrepyrolytic process. Pyrolytic char has a good calorific value that is equivalent to high-grade charcoal. They can be crushed or used in briquettes form. Treatment of industrial effluent plants has been suggested by using this char as this is low absorbents [8].

Figure 1 Tyre pyrolysis conversion products and applications

2.4. Steel Wires

The marketing of pyrolysis steel wire is mainly accompanied by the sanitation, quantity, and covering of the product. The purity of the product is determined by the contamination of rubber. The meticulous standard to market the steel is should be less than 9%. The steel can be improved by employing thermal processing the tyres with low or no rubber contamination. The pyrolytic process inclines the quality of the steel. It is very easy to separate the steel and carbon black. The process is so complex for the tyres in a chip for continuous pyrolysis, gasification, and liquefaction. From the residual sulphur, the steel products are extracted from the healthier steel [9].

3. Generation of Electricity

The waste unused tyres were made into pieces and loaded into the reactor. The speed of the reactor is about 0.4 to 0.8 revolutions per minute and rotates in the clockwise direction. The feeding inlet door should be verified for gas leakage and kept tight. The reactor should be heated by using fuel such as coal, charcoal, any fuel gas, diesel, etc. The oil gas will be produced by heating the reactor slowly to about 500 degrees. The oil gas generated in the reactor reaches the condensing system and becomes liquid oil. A safety device has been employed to send the gas to a combustion system that cannot be liquefied with normal pressure. Figure 2 presents the methodology to heat the reactor as fuel by recycling the same that will save energy. The excess heat in the form of uncondensed gas is fed to the gas engine coupled alternator to generate electricity that will be utilized for the factory lighting system.

Figure 2 Block diagram of Generation of electricity using Pyrolysis

The composition of the pyrolysis products is predisposed by the process operating conditions such as feed size, operating temperature and pressure, residence time, heating rate, and as well as the presence of a catalytic medium. The large feed-size pieces become carbonized yield char and cannot be decomposed. With the increase in temperature, there is an increase in gas yield. At the same time, there is an equal decrease in liquid due to evaporation. Then re-polymerization and carbonization react and make oil hydrocarbons into char. An increase in vapor dwelling time results in a decrease in liquid and char whereas, there is in an increase in gas to some extent [10].

4. Conclusion

This work reviews the process of pyrolysis, pyrolytic products, and generation of electricity. An increase in energy requirements, rigorous gas emissions, and reduction of fossil oil resources result to go for alternative fuels for internal combustion engines. Many swap fuels like Alcohol, Biodiesel, LPG, CNG, etc have been commercialized in the transport sector. In this background, pyrolysis of solid waste is currently receiving altered interest. The success of waste tyre pyrolysis also makes the product market easy to use. Pyrolysis of a substance offers a value-added product such as

pyrolysis oil that is used as lubrication for the high-capacity furnace and power transformers. The excess uncondensed gas is fed to the gas engine and made possible to generate electricity.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

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